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ABSTRACTS

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Identification and characterization of novel drug targets against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* using *in-silico* approaches

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Abstract: Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the key health problems in worldwide. The usage of anti-TB drugs for extended duration has increased the emergence of multidrug- (MDR) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains. Therefore to address the emerging risk of antibacterial resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains the development of compounds with new modes of action that engage unexploited drug targets can be considered. In the current study, tRNA modification enzymes which are known to facilitate the intracellular growth in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* were identified as novel drug targets. The sequence of tRNA modification enzymes of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* was fetched from the databases and was further explored for its conserved domain. The *in-silico* structure model was built for the novel tRNA modification sequence and was further validated. Furthermore, the modeled structure of tRNA modification enzymes will characterize for its binding affinity against novel antimicrobial agents with new mode of action using molecular dynamics simulation approaches will be carried out.

Keywords: *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, multidrug-resistance, tRNA modification, molecular dynamics.

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